

WAYS OF DEVELOPING SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: The purpose. The rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship is the main link that ensures the sustainable growth of the economy of any country and is the priority of the economic reforms being implemented. In our republic, ensuring the stability of small business and private entrepreneurship and supporting it is defined as one of the main priorities of the country's socio-economic development.

Methods. The important role of the small business sector in the economy is that it provides a competitive environment in the economy, supplies products and services for large enterprises, creates new jobs, increases the flexibility of the market system, accelerates scientific and technical progress, and mobilizes resources for production is determined by factors such as ensuring the increase in the volume of tax revenues, stabilizing the level of income of the population.

Results. To increase the contribution of small business to the country's economy, to create small industrial zones, to improve the investment environment and competitive environment, to expand the volume of public procurement within the framework of public-private partnership with small business, to strengthen mutually beneficial cooperation between large and small enterprises, involvement of business entities in innovation processes.

Conclusion. Based on the above tables and analysis, small business and private entrepreneurship subjects are able to overcome the world financial and economic crisis relatively easily due to their compact, mobile and quick flexibility, and life shows this. Therefore, it contributes to the development of entrepreneurship in every way. Support is desirable.

Keywords:.... small business, entrepreneurship, gross domestic product, tax, trade, goods.

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Introduction

Economic reforms aimed at the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, strengthening of its legal and regulatory foundations in the conditions of economic liberalization are considered to be one of the urgent issues.

The rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship is the main link that ensures the sustainable growth of the economy of any country and the priority direction of the ongoing economic reforms.

Based on the development of small business, a number of social and economic tasks are solved.

World experience shows that small business is the most important sector that fills the domestic market with necessary goods and services, determines the structural basis of the economy, and is the main factor and source for providing employment to the population and increasing its income serves.

In our republic, ensuring the stability of small business and private entrepreneurship and supporting it is defined as one of the main priorities of the country's socio-economic development.

The important role of the small business sector in the economy is that it provides a competitive environment in the economy, supplies products and services for large enterprises, creates new jobs, increases the flexibility of the market system, accelerates scientific and technical progress, and mobilizes resources for production is determined by factors such as ensuring the increase in the volume of tax revenues, stabilizing the level of income of the population.

Small business and private entrepreneurship as a form of economic activity are characterized by high universality, a wide range of activities, compactness and quick adaptability to any conditions. Therefore, it is not an exaggeration to say that the development of small business and private entrepreneurship is a guarantee of the stabilization of society and the increase of economic well-being.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said, "By an active entrepreneur, we mean business people who are able to produce competitive products, and most importantly, create new jobs and support not only themselves and their families, but also benefit the entire society.

Our first task is to expand the ranks of such entrepreneurs, including bringing and introducing high-tech, technology and equipment based on the latest achievements of science to our country.

If necessary, we should give them every opportunity to gain experience and mutually beneficial cooperation in leading foreign companies and organizations" [1]. It can be seen that entrepreneurship is creativity.

Methods

It helps to develop small business and private entrepreneurship in our republic.

1. Registration time of small business entities is 30 minutes. Only one document is required for registration as an individual entrepreneur, and two documents are required for registration of a small enterprise as a legal entity.

2. The tax payment rate, which is an important factor in creating favorable conditions for the development of small businesses in almost all sectors, is 5% of the volume of goods and services sold. The current rate of rent is 15%.

3. Financial support of small business is carried out in the following ways: granting loans by banks at preferential rates; guarantee of 50% of the loan funds given to entrepreneurial activities of the State Fund for Entrepreneurship Support and compensation of interest costs calculated on commercial bank loans.

4. Clusters for young entrepreneurs were organized by providing business training courses for entrepreneurs across the republic, implementing projects on the

basis of privatized facilities, and allocating plots of land on the basis of zero rent for a period of 5 years.

Such practical measures are giving their results. Small business provides about 60% of our country's gross domestic product, one third of the volume of industrial products, 98% of agricultural products, half of investments. In many regions, 70-90% of exports are made by small businesses. corresponds to business. In 6 months of this year, the number of business entities increased by 60 thousand.

At the same time, we should highlight the problems that prevent small businesses from fully realizing their potential.

1. In small business, more than 62% of employees are employed in individual businesses, while 16% belong to small enterprises and micro-firms. Low levels of employment of small enterprises: Navoi (11.3%), Kashkadarya (12.4%) and Tashkent region (13.2%).

If we look at the number of small business entities in the region, the largest number of entities are in the city of Tashkent (22.6%), Tashkent (9.6%), Fergana (8.8%) and Andijan (8.7%) regions are operating. About 50% of the total number of small business entities are operating in these four regions. It can be seen that Syrdaryo (3.2%), Navoi (3.3%) and Jizzakh (4.2%) in other regions of our republic, indicating that the existing potential of small business entities is not being used sufficiently.

This issue is analyzed in the section of small business entities in Andizhan region for 2020 and 2021.

Small business entities in the section of networks

Indicator of name	Number of small business entities	Share of total (%)	Jobs in them
total operating ones:	22560	100,0	92763
from that			
- agriculture	1813	8,0	5047
- industry	5494	24,4	33020
- construction	2414	10,7	13845
- trade	6780	30,1	17550
- in transportation and storage service	1063	4,7	8259
- in accommodation and food service	1282	5,7	4376
- Information and communication	514	16,5	1092
- provision of healthcare and social services	563	2,5	2695

- in other species	2637	11,9	6879

As it can be seen from the analysis of the above points in the cross-section of industries, we can see a relatively low level position of small business in the industrial sector with high efficiency of job creation compared to other industries.

The preservation of this indicator at the current level of growth may cause problems related to the increase of the population's wages and real income from business activities in the future.

This situation may lead to the restriction of social guarantees provided by the state to the population.

The share of small business entities in indicators of economic sectors in Andijan region (%)

Indicator of name	2020 year	2021 year
In the volume of production of industrial products	21,4	27,1
In agriculture, forestry and fisheries	97,8	97,6
In the amount of investments	59,8	54,8
In the scope of construction works	93,3	95,3
In retail circulation	88,5	90,3
In the services	67,7	65,4
In export	44,5	36,6
In import	12,9	13,1

The share of the number of small business entities in the trade remains at a high level. Retail trade, as of 2021, makes up 90.3% of the turnover. Construction works increased by 2%.

Results

In the development of small business in our country, construction and finishing materials, tools and equipment, machinery spare parts and equipment, electrical engineering, chemical, pharmaceutical products, production of many types of consumer goods, etc., are areas with high potential.

Increasing the contribution of small business to the country's economy, creating small industrial zones, improving the investment environment and competitive environment, expanding the volume of public procurement within the

framework of public-private partnership with small business, strengthening mutually beneficial cooperation between large and small enterprises, innovation we can see by involving business entities in the processes.

It is worth noting that it is important to provide financial support to successful and promising small enterprises that have sufficient export potential, but at the same time do not have enough capital for further development.

These measures help to create more jobs in the field of effective small business, increase access to the world market, increase the export potential of the country and increase the income of the population.

Discussions.

With the growth of small business and private entrepreneurship, the task of forming the middle class of owners, who are the backbone of the country, will be solved.

In general, small business and private entrepreneurship today are considered an important link that provides employment for the population and is its main source of income.

Therefore, it is important to implement and organize production on the basis of consumer requirements and to open a wide way for citizens to engage in entrepreneurship, to fully use their existing opportunities, to carry out entrepreneurial activities based on high efficiency, initiative and organization's attention is being paid.

Conclusions.

Small business and entrepreneurship play a major role in the social and economic development of Uzbekistan and occupy a leading position.

Because almost half of the gross domestic product created in the country and 57% of new jobs, 78.3% of the employed population and 70% of the population's income fall on this sector.

So, the social and economic development of the country depends on it, and it is one of the main forces determining its development.

Small businesses and private entrepreneurship entities are able to overcome the world financial and economic crisis relatively easily due to their compact, mobile and quick flexibility, and their lives show this. That is why the state supports the development of entrepreneurship in every way.

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